

TYPES OF TEACHING STRATEGIES AND ADVANCE INSTRUCTION STRATEGIES

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Abstract: In traditional education, the main teaching strategy was the direct transmission of knowledge from the teacher to the student. Students were considered passive subjects of information and their only role was to memorize information given by their teacher. Fortunately, teaching strategies today have evolved a lot and have addressed aspects such as student motivation, the visibility of meaningful learning, and the development of student potential through exploration and support. In this article, we will consider its most important features.

Key words: teaching strategies, learn, knowledge, education, university, training

Teaching strategies - teaching strategies are all resources used by the teacher to ensure meaningful learning for students. Their use is one of the main processes in the field of education, so they are used regardless of the theoretical basis of the lessons. Based on their importance, teaching strategies are used at all levels of the educational system, from preschool to the most advanced institutions such as universities. Their practical implementation varies depending on the context, but their principles are always the same.

1. The first type of teaching strategy includes all the methods used before acquiring knowledge. Its main goal is to prepare the student's mind for effective use of the educational process, to create new knowledge and to be able to make the most of the training. Pre-educational strategies can be very diverse and depend on the particular educational context in which they are used, as well as the characteristics of the student and the theoretical framework on which the training is conducted.

Some of them are aimed at updating previous knowledge, while others are aimed at organizing learning or connecting it with ideas that the student has previously acquired. For example, a very common teaching strategy before teaching is to work with the student to identify the learning objectives to be achieved in a particular activity. In this way, the process becomes more efficient, time is used efficiently, and the student can more easily consolidate what he has learned. Another good example is brainstorming with students on a specific topic. With this technique, students can check what previous ideas are related to what they want to see in class, making it easier for them to retain new information.

2. The second group of teaching strategies includes all strategies aimed at making the student pay as much attention as possible, feel eager to learn, and retain the information presented more easily. At the same time, they aim to achieve meaningful learning that lasts over time. Some of the cooperative learning strategies include the use of graphic or visual materials that increase student retention of information. For example, presenting a topic with a video accompanying an explanation can help students better understand what is being said. These types of teaching strategies can also include any method that helps students pay more attention and show interest in what they see in class. Thus, for example, at certain educational levels, the use of interesting games and problems can be fully adapted to this part of the educational process.

3- Post-training strategies. Post-teaching teaching strategies include all methods that help students retain content, think critically about what they have seen in the lesson, and resolve any doubts they may have about what they have learned. Post-learning strategies can be very diverse, as they include the preparation of concept maps or summaries of discussed topics, participation in discussions to reinforce acquired knowledge, resolve doubts or implement new ones concepts through the specific tasks they are designed to perform. On the other hand, in most cases, after-class teaching strategies also include reflection and critical thinking about what was learned in the lesson. This is especially true in higher education processes such

as university. Teaching strategies developed for working with children are primarily aimed at cultivating attention and fun, and provide students with knowledge related to their direct experiences. In this way, meaningful learning is created in an enjoyable way. One of the most used strategies in this sense is the game. Children naturally learn through play because this activity allows them to put themselves in different roles and understand their surroundings directly. A good teacher should be able to adapt this technique to the different learning situations he wants to create in the classroom.

Starting in adolescence, young people develop the ability to think abstractly and therefore can use more advanced learning strategies. But overall, it's important to motivate students and connect what they've learned to their own experiences. One of the most widely used teaching strategies in high school today is project-based learning. Instead of taking theoretical classes, students should develop their own work on a specific topic, thereby learning more about it. Once they enter college or reach a certain age, people have an easier time thinking critically and solving more complex problems. Therefore, most teaching strategies involve activities such as discussion, research, or large-scale projects.

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